

Final report of Science Shop in Gdańsk 2023

1.1. Expectations at the beginning of the pilot activity

Science Shops are not “shops” in the traditional sense of the word. They are small entities that carry out scientific research in a wide range of disciplines on behalf of citizens and local civil society and are free of charge. The fact that Science Shops respond to civil society’s needs for expertise and knowledge is a key element that distinguishes them from other knowledge transfer mechanisms. The Marine Science Shop will demonstrate how students and researchers can assist.

Marine Science Shop team meeting

Marine Science Shop (UG): University of Gdańsk will develop, test and run the Science Shop model. It brings students, researchers, and civil society together with the aim to tackle actual issues at the local and regional levels. The Marine Science Shop will provide an inclusive and safe space for participatory dialogue. This model will also create opportunities for twinning with existing science shops through e.g. The Living Knowledge Network or UNESCO Chair in Community Based Research and Social Responsibility in Higher Education. The Marine Science Shop will promote social inclusion and sustainability due to the nature of the activities which can link social groups and foster social cohesion. Aside from positively impacting the co-creation of solutions to real world problems, the process of societal engagement strengthens both the research process and its outcomes, thereby contributing to research excellence and acceptability of innovation outcomes. With the aim to share the concept of a Science Shop with the reSEARch-EU partners, UG will organise a webinar (M28) entitled “Community Driven Participatory Research and Education”. During the meeting, various tools for public engagement via Science Shop will be discussed. The participants (18 in total, from research and

administration departments) will take part in special training courses (divided into small modules, 5 days x 2 hours) conducted by the UG staff as well as the invited guests.

Third mission of the university and its cooperation with social actors is becoming more and more relevant. This can be seen on the EU policy level as well where the concept of open science or responsible research & innovation, community engagement, co-creation, and development of social innovation have been promoted since the last decade until today.

The vision was to develop the cooperation scheme between various units of the Pomerania Region and the University. Its main objective is a search for solutions to the local challenges through a model of the so-called Science Shop, which is an action scheme facilitating and ensuring an accomplishment of joint projects directed at the needs of social organizations which usually have a difficult access to scientific research.

1.2. Methodology and Development

It took a few months to develop the methodology and to select relevant organisations. The University of Gdańsk held a series of one-to-one meetings with representatives of different NGOs as part of the Marine Science Shop initiative. These face-to-face discussions took place both at the University and at the premises of the individual NGOs, enabling a better understanding of the specifics of each NGO's operation.

The objective of these meetings was not only to show the details of the Marine Science Shop project and discuss opportunities for cooperation, but also to hear the problems faced by the organisations and to understand their expectations of potential cooperation. The joint discussions allowed the cooperation model to be adapted to the individual needs of each organisation, increasing the chances of their effective and long-term involvement in the project. Meetings were held both at the university and at the premises of the NGOs involved in the project. This allowed us to better tailor the cooperation proposal to the individual needs of each NGO.

Meeting with the Dobry Deal/Good Deal initiative members at the University of Gdańsk

Meeting at the "WAGA" Association's head office in Gdańsk

In the case of the Marine Science Shop/Innovations Marina, we offered our pilot assistance to non-governmental organizations in the sphere of their cooperation with our students, who supervised by mentors and experts proposed solutions to the selected challenges submitted by organizations or local communities. This has given our students an opportunity to verify their knowledge in practice, and to acquire new competence and skills, especially transferable ones.

The organizations may have acquired a good partner with innovative ideas compatible with their goals, and the University may have got new challenges and investigation spheres.

A series of webinars have been organised as well with participants of more than 18 participants each:

- 24 April 2023 – Norbert Steinhaus, Bonn Science Shop: Science Shop model in practice
- 12 May 2023 – Anna Schmidt-Fiedler, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznan: From cooperation to co-creation. Science Shop Model at Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań
- 15 May 2023 – Joanna Morawska, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań: Co-creation and crowdmapping as tools for integrating society into climate change adaptation and mitigation plans.
- 25 May 2023 – Emma McKenna, Queen's Belfast University: Working with the community through Science Shop.
- 30 May 2023 – Reka Matolay, Corvinus University, Budapest: Corvinus Science Shop: a course project focused on community engaged research and learning portfolio.

Work and meetings conducted in reference to this deliverable/ milestone:

NGO: RC Foundation – Dobry Deal Project/Good Deal Project

From March 2023 to June 2023, a team from the Department of Marketing at the Faculty of Management at the University of Gdańsk cooperated with representatives of the RC Foundation and members of Dobry Deal/Good Deal initiative.

Representatives of RC Foundation and Paulina Stefańska, Bartosz Duraj

There were 5 meetings held:

- 1) The first one took place in the Sustainable Development Center UG and was attended by the main representatives of the foundation and the representatives Marine Science Shop project on behalf of the University of Gdańsk.
- 2) During the second meeting, the foundation presented its headquarters in Gdańsk to the team from the University of Gdańsk. The meeting was also attended by two marketing students via MS Teams – Natalia Rychta and Aleksandra Cielecka.
- 3) The third meeting was a creative brainstorming session, during which all participants met live and developed a detailed strategy. A consultant was also invited to the meeting - Mateusz Stefański, who is the creative director and event manager.
- 4) The fourth meeting was entirely coordinated by students - a photo session was held at the Foundation's headquarters. The purpose of the photo session was to present the assumptions and products related to the Good Deal project.
- 5) The fifth meeting was held in a hybrid form - it was a summary of activities and a conversation about the introduction of the project and innovative idea to reality.

Meeting with the RC Foundation – Dobry Deal Project/Good Deal Project

The details about Dobry Deal Project/Good Deal Project:

The social economy is a form of civic and social activity that pursues its goals social through public benefit activities or economic or educational activity or cultural.

It is a form of activity that serves:

- job creation for activation and reintegration into employment and society
- people at risk of social exclusion,
- provision of social services of general interest,

- implementation of public tasks in the field of local development.

The social economy is becoming more and more widespread, along with the growing need for change in a society that is constantly looking for new identities. It's the concept of democratic, a competitive and solidarity-based area of prosperity for all citizens. Customers play the key role in this concept. The mission of the Good Deal is to promote the idea of socially responsible purchasing and increasing awareness that every zloty spent can go to such entities, that will make the most of this impact. Good Deal explains to the clients that when they contribute to the initiative other people's lives are getting better and better, and at the same time they themselves gain something unique, created especially for them.

The name Good Deal hides not only an invitation to do a good business deal, but also it encourages people to take a look behind the scenes of the initiative. This is the first stationary store in Gdańsk selling products from social economy entities (PES), but also one of the few projects aimed at supporting the marketing of these entities. A good deal combines in business and educational elements. The team diagnosed such needs during talks with non-governmental organizations.

It's possible to see the offer of local PES at various city festivals, picnics and fairs. Sometimes there were several stands at city days or events organized by NGOs. All these were local actions, sometimes accidental. The space for online sales has not been used so far. PES do not have their online stores and do not conduct effective sales and marketing activities. The main reason is the lack of competences and funds.

Products of the Good Deal project partners

The Good Deal project has several Good Deal partners who offer unique products. These are regular partners, whose offer is in the store all year round, but also occasional ones who they appear, for example, around holidays or on the occasion of the Dominican Fair.

Examples of partnership and goods in Social Economy Store:

- Ceramics is created as part of occupational therapy workshops (WTZ) conducted by Efficient Differently Foundation. This organization has been working for over 30 years helping people with disability to function in society and appear on the market.
- Social Cooperative Zeroban - is the first social cooperative in Pomerania sewing various bags, sachets, panniers, cases, sacks, wallets made of unnecessary advertising materials – banners, roll ups, walls - and material samplers. Zeroban also gives a second life to people far from the market, offering them the possibility of earning a decent income. The cooperative promotes not only the ideas of social economy, but also less waste.

- Occupational Therapy Workshop operating within the Puck Association for the Support of People with Mental Disability provides the Project with beautiful, handmade candles and scented soaps.
- The Sensitive World Foundation, which runs Caffè Aktywni, produces for the Good Deal unique, decorated gingerbread.

During the meeting The Team talked, listened, identified needs. The first need presented by the NGO members concerned the problem of marketing and advertising. During meetings and brainstorming, it was possible to specify the actual needs and find innovative solutions. The idea of creating Mystery Charity Boxes for the foundation was born.

What is the Mystery Charity Box?

Our team noticed that there is a lot of this typical activities for all types of NGOs. We believe that the buyers are already used to buying small goods (cups, porcelain figurines, hand-painted baubles, dried flowers, silk scarves, etc.) as part of supporting groups working for charity initiatives.

Mystery Charity Box

The Mystery Charity Box is simple but innovative. It is a cardboard box, similar to what you can find in boutiques or drugstores, with the logo of NGO. Coherent visual identification is essential because the box is used not only for transport purposes. It has primarily a communication function and allows the brand to be associated with a wide range of buyers and friends of the entire movement.

The box contains a few pieces of products made by our NGOs participants. The boxes are divided into sizes (S, M and L), each of them contains 3 pieces, 5 or 10. The boxes are also divided by theme:

- wellness or SPA (here we pack bath salt, hand-made soap, beeswax candles, etc.)
- home decor (dried flowers, clay or porcelain decorations, coasters for cups, photo frames, etc.)
- fashion (handmade clothes, painted fabrics, recycled shopping bags, hairbands, etc.)
- baby or family (baby blankets, crocheted hats, crocheted toys, patchwork rugs for a baby's room, etc.)
- and many, many more other categories.

The most important marketing tool in this project is that these are surprise boxes. Buyers can only choose size and category. They don't know what they will get inside the package. Such boxes are very popular in the beauty industry, example: <https://shop.bygoodiebox.com/pl/collections/limited-editions>

Why do we think this is a better idea than creating a classic application with an online store and individual approach to each product?

- 1) we don't sell goods. We sell concepts and experience. This will go even to those who are not fans of needlework.
- 2) we have less work when it comes to product sessions, offer updates and the entire administration of the online store. We also avoid the problem of shortages in the assortment. After all, it's not a mass production... we have limited editions of everything. We also avoid stocking less popular products
- 3) it's something new, fresh, it will attract the attention of sponsors. Companies will be able to order boxes from the NGO for Christmas to give to their employees. Individual buyers will give their loved ones something unique.

We also want to add an important element to this project: each box would contain a photo (instax type) with a smiling people/person, a signature with the name and a short sentence: "I did it for you with joy!" or "Thank you for your support", etc.

NGO: "WAGA" Association

From March 2023 to May 2023, a team from the Institute of Psychology, Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Gdańsk and The Centre for Sustainable Development of the University of Gdańsk (CZRUG) collaborated with representatives of the "WAGA" Association. One in-person meeting as well as online consultations were held to assess the organization's needs and plan the actions addressing them.

First, Bartosz Duraj of CZRUG reached the NGO to propose participating in the Marine Science Shop project. Based on the association's initial interest, a meeting in the head office of the "WAGA" Association was scheduled on 14 May 2023. During the meeting, the representatives of the University of Gdańsk, Bartosz Duraj and Judyta Borchet, presented the basic assumptions of working in the Science Shop model and asked the NGO's representatives to present their challenges and areas in which they would welcome support.

Bartosz Duraj (CZRUG) and Dr. Judyta Borchet (Institute of Psychology, UG) with Elżbieta Jachlewska, Magdalena Paszkowska, and Tomasz Różyński of the "WAGA" Association

Interestingly, the NGO's needs were not in line with the University's presumptions and were related to a very specific action. "WAGA" stated that they could use some help during the organization of the career day for refugees from Ukraine. Finding a job is a key part of building immigrants' independence, self-agency, and financial security. The event aimed to help the refugees improve their position in the Polish job market by providing them with opportunities related to career guidance such as meeting HR specialists, underlining their strengths and professional experiences, and learning how to effectively create their vita.

The poster promoting the event – “Idę do pracy” (eng. I am starting to work/ going for work) workshop series

The University of Gdańsk addressed this need and proposed participating in the event and delivering a workshop related to shaping self-presentation skills and building positive self-image in the online environment, which are useful issues in terms of job interview performance. Details related to the workshop organization have been set during online communication among parties. In the meantime, Dr. Judyta Borchet started the recruitment process of a student that would be involved in the project.

On the 10 May 2023, a psychology student called Aleksandra Obuchowicz joined the project and was mentored by Dr. Borchet throughout the process. Aleksandra was introduced to the Marine Science Shop vision, the NGO's need for support during their event and proceeded to address in with Dr. Borchet. Under her supervision, Aleksandra prepared the script of workshop on auto presentation.

On 23 May 2023 the workshop was held. The content of the workshop covered not only topics such as non-verbal communication, the role of self-esteem in auto presentation, job interview performance, or creating personal image in social media but also stress management which is an important ability that can improve one's performance during the job interview.

Welcoming the participants

Exercises conducted during the workshop aimed not only for improving the auto presenttaion skills but also empowering them through highlighting their strengths, professional experience, and the variability of their stress management strategies.

The workshop was succesful as the participants and “WAGA” Association provided positive feedback. Both “WAGA” and UG are open for future collaboration.

The group and the trainers at work

Aleksandra Obuchowicz (UG), Magdalena Paszkowska (WAGA), and Judyta Borchet (UG) after the workshop

1.3. Challenges found and solution proposed

NGO: RC Foundation – Dobry Deal Project/Good Deal Project

The biggest difficulties are technical difficulties – during the photo session it was not possible to achieve satisfactory results because the photographer assigned from the NGO did not have sufficient qualifications. The team has a plan to repeat the photo shoot and try to find a funds for more qualified professionals.

NGO: “WAGA” Association

The main difficulty we have encountered was that the organization’s needs were not in line with our presumptions over the Marine Science Shop actions. We expected to work within the field of research but it turned out that other type of involvement is needed. The team decided that

the main goal of the Marine Science Shop is to address the NGO's needs as accurately as possible thus we decided to conduct the workshop during their event.

In addition, we have noticed how important it is to communicate our mission and activities effectively. During the course of the project, we realised that it is crucial not only to communicate our work, but also to tell captivating stories that inspire and engage. Professional storytelling tools and the involvement of communication specialists could be a good solution. This could increase our ability to create strong, engaging narratives that attract the attention of communities and NGOs.

We would invite students to participate in all our meetings regarding the Dobry Deal Project/Good Deal Project from the very beginning. They turned out to be an extremely important element in creating concepts and strategies.

We would make no presumptions on possible needs of the organization and be more elastic in thinking about those needs. The main goal of the project with the "WAGA" Association was to support the organization in the area they select, thus it is possible it would not relate to research – although immersed in science and education.

We believe that the action was well - planned and a detailed methodology was developed in consultancy with social partners.

1.4. Results obtained

corresponding to real needs. Our close cooperation with local NGOs has resulted in the creation of "tailor-made" solutions. The activities we proposed were well thought out and precisely tailored to the NGOs' needs.

Strengthening community involvement. Adopting the rules of participatory solution development, we intensified the involvement of NGOs, students and research and teaching staff.

Competency development and education. Working directly with academics and students enabled NGO members and those benefiting from their support to acquire new skills and knowledge.

Networking. The initiative has led to closer ties between NGOs, researchers and students, shaping sustainable networks. These relationships, which go beyond a single project, open up new opportunities for future initiatives that can bring even greater benefits to the local community.

The activities have contributed to addressing specific issues faced by the local community and NGOs, but have also built the foundations for long-term sustainable and integrated collaboration. We are ready to face the challenges ahead together.

The main result was to test and to learn from each other about different tools and methodologies related to the community engagement and building bridges between the science and the society.

On the university level the main benefit was the establishment of Marine Science Shop/ Innovation Marina as the pop-up contact point of cooperation between the university and the non-governmental organisations. Moreover, two organisations from the region: Stowarzyszenie Waga (more information: <https://stowarzyszeniewaga.pl/>)

Fundacja Regionalne Centrum Informacji i Wspomagania Organizacji Pozarządowych have declared a will to extend this cooperation into a strategic partnership and to continue this cooperation in the future with all the faculties of the university (more information: <https://fundacjarc.org.pl/>).

This action will be beneficial for the Alliance as it feeds the other projects implemented and contributes to the development of the Society Hub in SEA EU 2.0. It gives the opportunity of learning and exchanging various formats of community engagement.

1.5. Quality Self-Assessment

The joint efforts towards sharing and developing successful practices and cooperation models in research and innovation, aiming at impacting in a more meaningful and effective way have been met. A transformative role of universities acting across all three university missions and contributing to society through value co-creation, entrepreneurship, community-connected education and problem-oriented interdisciplinary research is one of the key goals of the Alliance and the reSEArch-EU project. The Science Shop model is in line with all those priorities mentioned above as it builds bridges with the society and incorporates society values and needs, and novel research questions into a university practice, according to the quintuple helix 'Science – Society – Business-Policymakers-the Environment' nexus, contributing to the competitiveness of industries and technology, and hence to the sustainable societal & economic development of the territories where it is located and which it serves.

The Science Shop model catalyzes innovation through trans-disciplinarity and explores different modes of societal actors' inclusion with a given regional / local context and a given topical issue. In our case we have conducted a region-wide survey dedicated to NGOs with the aim of investigating their needs and motivation for cooperation with the university. Moreover, the pilot actions have been agreed and conducted in a partnership with the communities in a two-way and mutual learning mode and not simple transfer of knowledge. In this sense, such a model of cooperation sheds the new light of third mission of the university and tests novel approach to incorporating researchers & students into a systemic policy towards building societal impact of science.

The results of the action are beyond our expectations as they brought not predicted and long-term impact in the shape of long-term and strategic cooperation with important societal players in the region. Moreover, the scientific & interdisciplinary article is about to be sent for publishing that investigates the role of universities in cooperation with the third sector and summarises the research done.

The NGO RC Foundation – Dobry Deal Project/Good Deal Project is open to further activities related to the University of Gdańsk. There was an idea to create an internship program for students of each of the UG faculties. As part of the discussion summarizing the project, the idea of creating an office acting as a "bridge" between NGOs and the scientific community was raised.

The project with the NGO "WAGA" Association benefited multiple parties. First, the workshop participants could shape their skills that can be useful during their professional development. Therefore, for them the workshop outcomes are potentially long-term and might increase their

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chances for finding a job and in turn – improving the quality of their life in Poland. Second, based on the fact that this collaboration between the University of Gdańsk and “WAGA” was a positive experience, both parties are open for future collaboration.

